

COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES OF NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Compressive properties of three different uni-directional natural fibre composites have been evaluated, based on flax, bamboo and coir fibres. It was found that bamboo fibre composites had the highest compression strength. If the compressive properties are compared to the tensile properties it can be seen that flax and bamboo composites reach between 60 and 80% of the tensile values, which means that the compression behaviour does not need to be of great concern. Coir fibre composites even perform better in compression than in tension.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in the use of natural fibres for composites. The main reasons are the ecological benefits combined with the good specific mechanical properties [1-10]. Because of the moisture sensitivity and the limited thermal resistance, the number of applications is still less than these properties would suggest [11, 12]. For different applications the compressive properties are also important, but these properties have been scarcely studied in literature. In [13] the compressive properties of flax fibres were studied. In this paper the compressive properties of composites with different natural fibres will be presented and compared with their tensile properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Three different fibres were used: flax fibres were supplied by Lineo in the form of the unidirectional Flaxtape product. The flax fibres need to be dried for 24h at 60°C.

The technical bamboo fibres which were used to produce the bamboo-epoxy-composites were of the species *Guadua angustifolia*, obtained from a bamboo plantation in Colombia. A wet cleaning process is applied in which the fibres are combed to remove the parenchyma cells. This also results in an alignment of the fibres. After cleaning, the fibres should be dried for 72h at 60°C [14].

The coir fibres used to produce the coir-epoxy-composites were provided by Can Tho University in Vietnam. These are long coir fibres which have a length between 200 and 300 mm. The fibres were obtained from the coconut husk using mechanical extraction. The same cleaning process which was applied for the bamboo fibres, was used for the coir fibres, as well as the method of drying the fibres.

The matrix used in combination with the natural fibres consisted of epoxy resin (Epikote 828 LV) in combination with 1,2-diaminocyclohexane hardener (Dytek DCH-99). These two components are mixed in a ratio of 15.2g of hardener per 100g of resin. The resin should be degassed before it is used for the production of the composites. All of the natural fibre composites which were produced had a fibre volume fraction of 40%.

2.2 Methods

The method used for the production of the unidirectional fibre composites was Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI). A mould with a top and bottom plate was used which resulted in the production of composite plates with a thickness of 2 and 4mm. The infusion was performed at a temperature of 40°C. When the impregnation was complete, the temperature was increased to 70°C to start the curing process for 1h. The post curing was done for 1h at a temperature of 150°C in a separate

furnace.

Tensile tests were performed according to ASTM 3039 with a sample size of 230 x 12.7 x 2 mm³ and a test span of 150 mm. An extensometer was used. The compression tests were performed according to ASTM D3410. The sample dimensions were 135 x 10 x 4 mm³. The span of the compression samples was set to 15 mm. The samples for the mechanical tests were obtained by cutting the plates with a diamond saw. End tabs were used for the flax and the bamboo composite samples, while no end tabs were used for the coir composite. During compressive testing of the coir composites, the end tabs loosened, but satisfactory results were obtained by inserting sand paper between the clamps and the samples, without using any end tabs.

The compression tests were performed using an Instron 5985 testing device in combination with strain mapping by Digital Image Correlation (Limes) at both sides of the samples. The test speed used for the compression test was 1.5 mm/min. For one sample, two moduli and strains can be determined, one for the front and one for the backside. These are averaged to determine the modulus and strain for the composite. For each of the samples, also the percentage of bending (B_y) is determined. In agreement with the standard, only the samples with a percentage bending between -10% and +10% are considered. B_y is determined by following formula:

$$B_y(\%) = \frac{\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

where ε_1 is the frontside strain and ε_2 is the backside strain.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The overall resulting compressive stress-strain curves of the natural fibre-epoxy composites can be found in Figure 1. The graphs indicate that the flax and bamboo composites show similar stiffness behavior, and are much stiffer compared to the coir composite. The bamboo composite has the highest strength, followed by the flax composite, and the coir composite is the weakest.

Figure 1: Typical stress-strain graphs of compression tests on the UD composites with 3 different natural fibres.

The compressive properties of the natural fibre-epoxy composites with a fibre volume fraction of 40% are once more summarized in Table 1. The compressive strength is the maximum compressive stress which is reached during the test. The moduli of the flax and bamboo composites are similar and

much larger than the modulus of the coir composite.

	Compressive strength (MPa)	Compressive modulus (GPa)
Flax-epoxy	136.9 ± 5.5	15.1 ± 2.5
Bamboo-epoxy	149.5 ± 8.9	15.5 ± 2.7
Coir-epoxy	116.2 ± 5.8	3.7 ± 0.3

Table 1: Compressive properties of UD composites with different natural fibres with a fibre volume fraction of 40%.

All of the tested flax composite samples seem to have failed in a similar way, as well as most of the bamboo composite samples; the composite samples kink, because of the micro-buckling of the technical fibers.

The coir composite samples failed much more violently and showed a different failure behaviour. Their failure seems to be caused by the brittle nature of the epoxy. The early cracks which occur in the epoxy matrix during compressive testing are pressed together so they do not propagate. Close to failure of the composite, buckling can occur which causes the matrix cracks to propagate violently through the composite and cause breakage of the fibres. There is no micro-buckling appearing in the coir fibres.

A comparison can be made between the tensile and compressive properties of the different natural fibre-epoxy composites. The strength ratio and modulus ratio can be determined, which are the ratio between the compressive and tensile strength, and the ratio between the compressive and tensile modulus, respectively. The tensile properties for the flax- and bamboo-epoxy composites with a fiber volume fraction of 40% are given in Table 2 and compared to the compressive properties.

	Flax Tensile properties	Flax Compressive properties	Ratios for Flax (%)	Bamboo Tensile properties	Bamboo Compressive properties	Ratios for Bamboo (%)
Strength (MPa)	222.9 ± 6.1	136.9 ± 5.5	61.4	254.7 ± 18.3	149.5 ± 8.9	58.7
Modulus (GPa)	23.9 ± 1.9	15.1 ± 2.5	63.2	19.5 ± 1.0	15.5 ± 2.7	79.5

Table 2: Comparison of tensile and compressive properties for flax and bamboo UD composites with equal fibre volume fractions of 40%.

The strength ratio for the flax composite is thus equal to 61.4%, while its modulus ratio is equal to 63.2%. This means that for the flax composite, about 60% of its tensile properties are maintained during compression. The strength ratio of the bamboo is equal to 58.7%, but a larger modulus ratio of 79.5% is obtained. The good stiffness performance of the bamboo composite during compression might be due to the structure of the bamboo fibres, which combine an almost zero micro-fibrillar angle in the secondary cell wall of their elementary fibres with a 90° micro-fibrillar angle in their outer primary cell wall [15], thus providing an outer wrap for the 0° fibrils.

The comparison for coir composites is made based on results of [16]. It is more difficult because these tensile samples had a fiber volume fraction of 49%. The obtained tensile modulus and strength were 2.95GPa and 34.9 MPa respectively. Neglecting the difference in V_f this gives a modulus ratio of 125% and a strength ratio of 332% which means that the coir-epoxy composite performs very well in compression compared to the tensile behavior. In tension, cracks in the brittle epoxy propagate relatively easily through the fibers; in compression, critical early cracks are presumably closed, which delays failure of the sample.

As a benchmark, the strength ratio for UD glass fibre composites can be determined using the data of [17]. The tensile strength was 700 MPa and the compression strength 570 MPa, leading to a

strength ratio of 81%, which shows that the performance of the flax and bamboo composites is somewhat reduced compared to glass fibre composite, but perhaps not to the level to raise major concerns.

In previous research [14], longitudinal 3-point bending properties were determined for bamboo fibre epoxy composites. Also, single fibre properties were determined at a modulus of 43 GPa and a fibre strength of 800 MPa. Thus, the expected modulus and strength values for the uni-directional composites with a fibre volume fraction of 48% were 22.2 GPa and 384 MPa respectively. Measured values were 21.1 GPa and 310 MPa respectively. So, the strength efficiency factor was 80.7%. Because in flexural tests, there are as high compressive stresses as tensile stresses in the centre part of the beam, these results already indicated that there was not a particular concern about the compressive properties of bamboo fibre composites. This conclusion has been confirmed in the present study by performing direct compression tests on these composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the compressive properties of UD composites with three different natural fibers are compared and related to their tensile properties. It is shown that bamboo and flax perform better than coir fibers in absolute terms. If the results are compared to the corresponding tensile values it are the coir fibres which perform the best.

Compared to glass fiber composites it can be seen that the natural fibre composites perform less in compression. Also the strength ratio between compression and tensile strength is higher for glass fiber composites. However, the performance in compression for the natural fiber composites can be classified as decent with strength ratios of around 60%.

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